

Metal free C-O bond formation in electron deficient aromatic compounds mediated by tetrabutylammonium hydroxide : Application to nimesulide and paracetamol

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Abstract : A mild and efficient method for carbon-oxygen bond formation for the synthesis of aryl ethers has been demonstrated using stoichiometric amount of alcohol and tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBAH). The protocol is free from the metal alkoxides, inorganic bases or metal catalysts. This methodology has been applied for synthesis of paracetamol and nimesulide intermediates.

Keywords : Aryl ethers, phenols, TBAH, metal free C-O bond formation, tetrabutylammonium hydroxide.

Introduction

Tetrabutylammonium hydroxide (TBAH) is a simple organic liquid consist mixture of organic and inorganic counter ions such as tetrabutylammonium cation ion (Bu_4N^+) as well as hydroxyl anion (^-OH). So that TBAH can be utilized as base or nucleophile or ionic liquid or phase transfer catalyst based on synthetic utilization.

Aryl ethers and phenols are core structural units in a wide range of natural products, pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals and organic materials. Current methods for the preparation of aryl ethers (Scheme 1) are (1) nucleophilic aromatic substitution with alkoxides¹, (2) etherification with Lewis acids², (3) transition metal catalyzed cross coupling reactions³.

Scheme 1. General methods for preparation of aryl ethers.

Most of the above reaction protocols involve harsh reaction conditions such as high temperatures and strong bases. Usually, alkali metal alkoxides used in the above

reactions are moisture sensitive and sometimes pyrophoric in nature. In addition, these reactions require highly polar aprotic solvents and inert atmosphere.

Tetrabutylammonium hydroxide and Triton B are well known phase transfer catalysts and also used as bases^{4,5} for making alkoxides. However the formation of alkoxide anion is not well studied in any of the above reports.

Results and discussion

We are reporting facile C-O bond formation between aromatic chloro compounds and alcohols mediated by TBAH. This methodology has also been applied for the synthesis of nimesulide and paracetamol intermediates.

To establish the formation of alkoxide anions in presence of TBAH, we have conducted ¹H NMR experiments at the beginning. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-*d*₆) of benzyl alcohol in the presence of water showed two characteristic signals; a doublet at δ 4.48 (*J* 5.6 Hz) for benzylic protons and a triplet at δ 5.59 (*J* 5.6 Hz) for hydroxyl proton (Fig. 1). However the ¹H NMR of benzyl alcohol in the presence of stoichiometric amount of TBAH (40% w/w solution in water) showed a sharp singlet at δ 4.48 and the hydroxyl proton signal at δ 5.59 completely disappeared (Fig. 2). This experiment proves *in situ* formation of benzyloxy ammonium salt following the mechanism suggested below (Fig. 3).

Fig. 1. ¹H NMR of benzyl alcohol in absence of TBAH.

Fig. 2. ¹H NMR of benzyl alcohol in presence of TBAH.

drug nimesulide (*N*-(4-nitro-2-phenoxyphenyl)methanesulfonamide). All the reported synthesis of nimesulide involves the use of aryl ether **2c** (Scheme 2).

The existing methods⁷ for the synthesis of **2c** are less efficient which involves use of metal catalysts, strong bases and very high temperature. On other hand, when **2** was treated with phenol in the presence of TBAH at 70–75 °C for 12 h, intermediate **2c** was obtained in very high yield (92%). While making the aryl ethers from **1**, **2** and **3** using alcohol/TBAH mixture according to our new protocol, we observed the corresponding phenols in reaction mass in trace amount. This could be only possible if TBAH acts as a source for hydroxyl anion. This encouraged us to explore the use of TBAH as a source of hydroxy nucleophile to make biologically important phenols. The most common over the counter medicine paracetamol is usually prepared from 4-nitrophenol **1i** (Scheme 3).

The existing methods⁸ for the preparation of 4-nitrophenol **1i** via nitration of phenol suffers from poor regio selectivity and yield. Other methods⁹ for the preparation of **1i** from 4-halo nitrobenzene involve strong bases, use of metal catalysts and high temperature. On the other hand, intermediate **1i** has been prepared in near quantita-

Fig. 3. Proposed mechanism for generation of alkoxides and aryl ethers.

Once the formation of alkoxide anion was established, we thought of exploring the use of the alkoxides as nucleophiles. Various alkoxy nucleophiles were generated *in situ* from the corresponding alcohols and TBAH and treated with electron deficient aromatic halides such as **1**, **2** and **3** (Fig. 4) to prepare several aryl ethers (Table 1). This protocol worked well with primary and secondary alcohols but failed with tertiary alcohols probably due to steric reasons.

Once the methodology for ether formation was established, we thought of exploring the possibility of applying this methodology for preparation of biologically important molecules. A closer look at marketed medicines revealed the presence aryl ethers in anti-inflammatory

Fig. 4. Electron deficient aromatic halides **1**, **2** and **3**.

Substrate	Alcohol	Product	Yield (%)
1	CH ₃ -OH	O-CH ₃ (1a)	95 ^a
1	<i>n</i> -C ₂ H ₅ -OH	O-(<i>n</i> -C ₂ H ₅) (1b)	90 ^a
1	<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇ -OH	O-(<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇) (1c)	90 ^a
1	(Ph)CH ₂ -OH	O-CH ₂ (Ph) (1d)	89 ^a
1	(CH ₃) ₂ CH-OH	O-CH(CH ₃) ₂ (1e)	72 ^a

Table-1 (contd.)

1	(Ph)(CH ₃)CH-OH	O-CH(Ph)(CH ₃) (1f)	68 ^a
1	(CH ₃) ₃ C-OH	O-C(CH ₃) ₃ (1g)	Nil
1	(Ph)(CH ₃) ₂ C-OH	O-C(Ph)(CH ₃) ₂ (1h)	Nil
2	CH ₃ -OH	O-CH ₃ (2a)	88 ^b
2	<i>n</i> -C ₂ H ₅ -OH	O-(<i>n</i> -C ₂ H ₅) (2b)	86 ^b
2	Ph-OH	O-Ph (2c)	92 ^b
3	CH ₃ -OH	O-CH ₃ (3a)	69 ^{c,d}
3	<i>n</i> -C ₂ H ₅ -OH	O-(<i>n</i> -C ₂ H ₅) (3b)	71 ^{c,d}
3	<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇ -OH	O-(<i>n</i> -C ₈ H ₁₇) (3c)	80 ^{c,d}
3	(Ph)CH ₂ -OH	O-CH ₂ (Ph) (3d)	84 ^{c,d}

^aReaction carried out at ~20 °C for 6 h. ^bReaction carried out at 45–50 °C for 12 h. ^cReaction carried out at ~20 °C for 30 min. ^dIsolated yield of desired isomer.

Scheme 2. Synthesis of nimesulide.

Scheme 3. Synthesis of paracetamol.

tive yield (90%) from **1** using stoichiometric amounts of TBAH under mild reaction conditions¹⁰.

Conclusion

We have demonstrated the use of TBAH as base as well as nucleophile for the synthesis of aryl ethers and phenols. Various alkoxide anions were generated under mild conditions and were used to make variety of aryl ethers. This methodology was also applied for the synthesis of key intermediate for nimesulide. The nucleophilic nature of TBAH was utilized for the synthesis of 4-nitrophenol, an intermediate for paracetamol. This methodology is mild, operationally simple, does not require harsh or stringent reaction conditions and essentially avoids metals/metal catalysts. This methodology should find wider application for synthesis of aryl ethers and phenols.

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- General experimental procedure for the preparation aryl ethers : Alcohol (7.0 mmol) was added to a mixture of TBAH (6.75 mmol) and DMSO (5 mL) at 22 to 24 °C followed by addition of aryl halide **1**, **2** and **3** [(6.35 mmol) dissolved in 5.0 mL of DMSO]. The resulted reaction mixture continued for stipulated time period (see Table 1 foot note). Upon completion (monitored by HPLC) of the reaction, the reaction mass was added to ice-cold water (40 mL) and product was extracted into mass and the product was extracted with DCM (20 mL). The organic layer was separated; dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, afford the corresponding aryl ether by solvent evaporation.
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- Experimental procedure for the preparation of 4-nitrophenol (**1i**) : Mixture of TBAH (7 mmol) and DMSO (5 mL) was added to a solution of aryl halide **1** [(6.35 mmol) dissolved in 5.0 mL of DMSO] at 22 to 24 °C. The resulting mixture was stirred at 50 to 55 °C for 12 h. Upon completion (monitored by HPLC) of the reaction, the reaction mass was added to ice-cold water (80 mL). The product was filtered and washed with water (10 mL) to afford the product **8** as tetrabutylammonium salt, resulted product was acidified to pH ~2 with aqueous hydrochloric acid (10 mL) at 40 °C for 2 h and extracted the product with DCM (20 mL), yellow crystalline product was isolated by solvent evaporation with a yield of 90%.